

Speculation on the Presence of Environment and Particle Systems in the E,B Fields of a Moving Charge

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Newtonian mechanics seems to usually focus on two systems, a conservative force system (potential energy) and a particle system (kinetic energy). In such a case, one may change the sign of both force and $v, dv/t$ and obtain a time reversed picture as potential energy is converted into kinetic or vice versa. An exception to this scenario is friction and even though this was well known-long ago, it was not until the 1800s that thermodynamic equations were developed.

We suggest here that thermodynamics, at least in some cases, may be associated with a third entity which we call the environment (separate from force). The environment, unlike force and $v, dv/dt$ need not contain an observable which may switch sign and so breaks time reversal symmetry. In other words, it is coupled to the force and charge system, but only in a "receiving" manner. We suggest that even though a static source charge creates a Newtonian conservative force $-q_1 \text{ grad } \phi$, Maxwell's equations describe E,B (electric, magnetic fields) for both a particle system and an environment. The particle linked fields require sources and drop-off in a certain manner ($1/r^2$ or higher r) whereas E and B fields of the environment do not require sources and drop-off differently ($1/r$ is fine).

Maxwell already showed that his em equations give rise to a solution for a photon in the absence of sources. We suggest that even in the presence of sources, one may seek E, B solutions for which $\text{Grad dot } E = 0$ (using $t-R/c$, i.e. retarded time). We argue that such a solution would be part of the environment and try to show that the situation of an accelerating charge allows for such environmental E,B fields to appear. In such a situation, one has three systems, the force system, particle system and environment system, but unlike the force-particle system with its reversal of sign for $F, v, dv/dt$, energy appearing in the environment is lost because it is not in any way bound to the charge or the force system either. Hence, the creation of entropy is really the appearance of energy in a third system, the environment which is normally considered as part of the physical picture (i.e. of the force and particle system scenario).

Newtonian Mechanics and Force-Particle Systems

Time reversal is often linked with Newtonian mechanics for conservative forces ($F = -\text{grad } V(x)$) and particle systems. In such a case, potential energy is converted into particle kinetic energy and vice versa. There is time reversal symmetry because:

F may change to $-F$ and $v, dv/dt$ to $-v, -dv/dt$ ((1)).

The force and the particle are usually coupled forever if one has $V(x)$ as in a particle on a spring etc. The change of sign happens naturally as v becomes 0 at one point, but there is still a force and the particle changes direction.

An exception to this scenario is the case of friction. In such a situation, there still exist force and particle systems, but there is a third system, the environment, which does not interact with the particle (e.g. the interior of the floor with a surface creating friction). This environment is not described by a quantity which may change sign (if a movie is run backwards), but it may receive energy. It, however, does not return it because it is not linked to the friction force in the way that potential energy is linked to force ($F = -\text{grad } \phi$). In other words, one has an increase in temperature and the creation of entropy. Even though the idea of friction was known early, it was not until the 1800s that thermodynamic equations were written.

Electromagnetism and an Accelerating Charge

It is well-known that an accelerating charge radiates photons. The usual solution (1) is to calculate ϕ (electrostatic potential) and A (magnetic vector potential) using retarded time $t - R/c$. Here $R = |\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|$, with \mathbf{r} vector being the vector from a fixed origin to a measurement point and \mathbf{r}' vector being from the same origin to a piece of charge. A signal is said to move from a charge piece to the measurement point with c , the speed of light in a vacuum.

One then calculates:

$$E = -\text{grad } \phi - \frac{dA}{dt} \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{and} \quad B = \text{grad} \times A \quad ((2b))$$

It is found (1) that for an accelerating charge:

$$\phi \text{ contains a term proportional to: } \mathbf{r} \cdot \frac{dp}{dt}(t-r/c) / (cr) \quad ((3a))$$

$$\text{and } A \text{ a piece proportional to } \frac{dp}{dt}(t-r/c) / r \quad ((3b))$$

$$\text{This leads to: } E = \frac{u_0}{4\pi \epsilon_0} \left\{ -\frac{d}{dt} \frac{dp}{dt} + \mathbf{r} \cdot \frac{d}{dt} \frac{dp}{dt} \right\} \quad ((3c))$$

Here p is the dipole moment, $q\mathbf{l}$ for a point charge (where l is the distance from the origin to the charge) and so $dp/dt = qv$.

Other pieces with higher r drop-off exist. Thus, when using grad on ϕ , it converts to $1/c \, d/dt$ and if acceleration exists, one has a piece of E that drops as:

$$\text{Acceleration } C_1 / r \quad \text{where } C_1 \text{ is a constant} \quad ((4))$$

Similarly, there is a piece of B which drops as $1/r$. Using $\mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$ as proportional to momentum density, one finds that em density leaves the system even if one creates a sphere at $r \rightarrow \infty$.

This is the usual calculation of radiation and does not involve any discussion of thermodynamics, entropy production or environment (even though the radiated photons move into the environment).

$$\text{We wish to discuss this same situation using } \text{Grad} \cdot E = \text{charge density}/\epsilon_0 \quad ((5)).$$

Accelerating Charge and the Environment System

It may be immediately noticed that an accelerating charge contains a force system (accelerating the charge) and the particle system (charge). Normally, these two systems would suffice for a Newtonian mechanical description of the situation. One could reverse the signs of F and v , dv/dt and have a time reversible situation.

The problem, we argue, is that Maxwell's equations describe both a particle system and the environment, even if only applied to a moving charge by itself. In such a case, E and B describe the E and B fields of the charge and the environment. One would think that such a situation describes only a particle system. Maxwell, however, showed that he could obtain a photon solution (wave solution for both E and B), by setting charge density and current density terms to 0. In the accelerating charge situation, one does not set charge or current density to zero, but that does not prevent one from having E or B terms in the solution which act as if there were no source under particular circumstances (i.e. the grad acting only dipole moment pieces in E field expressions.). We examine:

$$\text{Grad dot } E = \text{charge density}/\epsilon_0 \text{ ((5a))} \rightarrow \text{grad dot } E = 0 \text{ ((5b))}$$

We ask whether there exists a piece of E which satisfies ((5b)). For an electrostatic problem, one has spherical symmetry and $\text{grad dot } E$ becomes $E \cdot \text{area surface vector normal to the surface}$. This surface integral must yield the charge within and so E goes a $r \text{ vector} / (r^2)$. Thus, E is strictly associated with the particle system and there is no environment system.

In the case of motion, one may consider to first order a $q \text{ r vector}/(r^2)$ (so that $\text{Grad dot } E$ converted to a surface integral returns charge/ϵ_0) plus corrections using multipoles. The first correction is a dipole one $p=ql$, but given that there is motion, it is possible to have:

$$dp/dt = qv \text{ and } d/dt dp/dt = q dv/dt \text{ in the case of acceleration ((6))}$$

((3c)) shows that one may have E field terms which drop as $1/r$, i.e. are not part of the q charged particle system which should drop as $1/r^2$ so that $\text{grad dot } E = q/\epsilon_0$. One may see that $\text{grad dot } E$ with grad acting only $d/dt dp/dt$ yields 0 for the constant acceleration case.

In the case for which acceleration is not 0, if one considers only the terms of $\text{grad dot } E$ which act on $d/dt dp/dt (t-r/c)$, one has again 0 i.e.:

$$\{ \text{grad dot } E \text{ with grad only acting on } d/dt dp/dt \text{ in ((3c)) yields } -1/r (-1/c) dr/dx (d/dt dp/dt) + (-1/c) dr/dx d/dt d/dt dp/dt (1/r) \}$$

Thus, having $\text{grad dot } E = 0$ pieces seems to indicate energy in the environment, i.e. decoupling of the field from the source charge q (even though the value of q is in the dipole moment p and so q governs how much radiation is created.)

The fact that one has E terms which do not drop as $1/r$, however, seems to be enough to indicate that energy is moving into the environment. There is no force which may pull this em energy back to the charge and so one has no time reversal and one may say that entropy is created. In fact, one now has three systems with energy instead of two and it seems that Maxwell's em equations allow the E,B fields of a moving charge to couple to the environment in one direction, i.e. there can be energy flow out of the charge system and into the environment with no time reversal pulling the energy back in because there is no force constraint to do this.

Why Should Maxwell's EM Equations For a Particle Include the Environment?

Maxwell's em equations mathematically describe experimental results and are constraint equations. If one were to apply them only to a moving charge, one might ask: Why should there be any considerations of the environment? We argue that Maxwell's em equations are closely linked to special relativity (in fact Lorentz found the Lorentz transformation by studying them). Thus, we speculate that the notion of both particle and environment systems being included in Maxwell's equations, even when it describes only a moving charge, is somehow associated with special relativity. This suggests that the production of entropy in the case of an accelerating charge should also be linked to special relativity.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest that usual Newtonian mechanics focuses on two systems, the conservative force and particle systems and ignores an environment system because it neither receives nor gives energy. One may reverse the sign of F (force) and v , dv/dt and obtain a time reversible picture. The environment, however, has no measurement variable whose sign may be changed because it is not acting on the particle system like the force. Thus, energy is lost to the environment and entropy produced.

We apply these ideas to the accelerating charge system. At first one might expect two systems, the force and particle, as E and B fields seem to belong to the charged particle system. The issue is that Maxwell's equations allow for environment E and B solutions as Maxwell already showed by finding a solution for a photon by setting charge and current densities to 0. (This result may be due to the equations being consistent with special relativity.)

For a moving charge system, charge and current densities are not zero, but there are two terms of E which are proportional to: $d/dt dp/dt / r$. First of all, these do not drop as $1/r$ which is needed so that $\text{grad dot } E$ converted into a surface integral over a sphere yields the charge inside divided by ϵ_0 . Secondly, if one applies grad in $\text{grad dot } E$ only the $d/dt dp/dt(t-r/c)$ pieces, then $\text{grad dot } E = 0$ for any acceleration. This also suggests a decoupling of E, B fields from the charge with energy moving to the environment. The environment, however, is not acting on the charge system, like a force does and so reversing the sign of v , dv/dt does not mean that one reverses the sign of the direction of motion of the radiated photons. These are lost to the environment and one has entropy production.

References

1. Reitz, J. and Milford, F and Christy, J. Foundations of Electromagnetic Theory (Addison Wesley, 1980)